

Effect of Non-equilibrium Solvation Dynamics on Photochemical Reactions in Solution[†]

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In many photochemical (or photophysical) reactions in solution, the electronic relaxation rate is of the same order of magnitude as the solvent relaxation rate. In such a situation the electronic relaxation rate may depend critically on the details of the solvent relaxation. Recent picosecond laser spectroscopy experiments have unambiguously showed the importance of such solvation dynamics and have revealed qualitatively several new aspects of solvent effects. Some of these effects cannot be explained by the traditional transition state theories which assume that solvent is at equilibrium with the reactive motion at every stage of the reaction. Recent experiments have also indicated an apparent breakdown of Kramers' theory for the viscosity dependence of rates of these ultrafast processes. In this article, we present new theoretical calculations to explore the effects of the non-equilibrium solvation dynamics on the reaction rates of these processes. We also consider the effect of 'memory' of solvent forces on reaction rates. These 'memory effects' may play an important role in the breakdown of Kramers' theory.

MOST known chemical reactions take place in the liquid phase. The various effects of solvent on chemical reactions have been studied extensively over the years¹⁻⁵. Recent advances in picosecond laser spectroscopy have added a new dimension to this field^{6,7}. It is now possible to study ultrafast processes where reaction rates lie in the picosecond or in the subpicosecond regime. This allows one to study the role of solvent forces on short time scales. Recent experimental studies have concentrated on understanding the role of solvent viscosity on reaction rate⁸⁻¹⁰ and also on the effect of solute-solvent interactions on the reaction potential energy surface^{9,11}. On the theoretical side, attempts have been made to extend and generalise the stochastic theories of reaction rate¹²⁻¹⁴ with various degrees of success in explaining the experimental results.

In this paper we consider two aspects of the solvent effects. Firstly, we consider the non-Markovian effects on chemical reactions in solution. Secondly, we study the effects of non-equilibrium solvation dynamics on chemical reactions.

The motivation for the study of the non-Markovian effects comes from recent experimental results^{9,10} which reveal an apparent failure of the well known Kramers' theory to explain the viscosity dependence of isomerisation reactions in solution. The experiments of Velsko *et al.*^{9,10} and of others⁹ reveal a significantly smaller effect of viscosity on rates at high viscosities than that predicted by Kramers' theory. It has been argued that the experimentally observed partial saturation of the viscosity effects arise from the frequency dependence of the frictional forces that inhibit barrier

crossings^{9,14}. For sharp barriers the *effective* friction in the barrier region can be much smaller than its zero frequency value at high viscosities. In this paper we present a treatment of these non-Markovian effects in a form which is somewhat different from what exists in the literature^{9,14}.

The second topic addressed in this paper is the effect of non-equilibrium solvation dynamics on reaction rate in solution. The central idea here is that for ultrafast reactions, the solvent molecules may not be able to follow the reaction and as a result, the reaction may occur from a state of incomplete equilibration with the solvent. The non-equilibrium solvation may play an important role in those chemical reactions which occur in polar media and where significant change in the value of the permanent dipole moment occurs in the course of the reaction. Since the polar forces are long ranged, they are usually slow to respond to the changes in the polar character of the reacting molecule. This may lead to significant non-equilibrium effects which are not treated in the standard transition state based theories.

The organisation of the rest of the paper is as follows: the general ideas and the concepts, consideration of the non-Markovian effects, the non-equilibrium solvation dynamics considered at length, and concludes with a brief discussion.

General considerations :

In this section we briefly discuss the theories and the concepts that are used to describe chemical reactions in the liquid phase.

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Transition state theory: The transition state theory (TST) is the earliest theory for chemical reactions in solution. The transition state is identified with an imaginary 'dividing surface' separating the reactant and the product states in the configuration space. For a one-dimensional potential surface, the transition state is usually chosen to be the state with the maximum energy in the barrier region. The basic assumption of TST is that once the reacting system crosses the transition state, it *never* returns to the same state again. It can be shown that when TST is not exact, it *overestimates* the exact, equilibrium rate constant^{55,56}.

The general expression for the TST rate constant is given in terms of partition functions of the transition state, the reactants and the products¹⁻⁴. However, for chemical reactions in solution this general expression is of little use because of the difficulties in evaluating the partition functions. The usual procedure is to express the rate constant in terms of thermodynamic functions which are accessible experimentally. The following well known expression was derived by Wynne-Jones and Eyring⁵,

$$k_{TST} = \frac{k_B T}{h} e^{\Delta S^\ddagger/h} e^{-\Delta H^\ddagger/k_B T} \quad (1)$$

where, ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger are the entropy of activation and the enthalpy of activation per molecule, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, h is the Planck's constant and T the temperature. It is a standard procedure to relate ΔH^\ddagger to energy of activation. For many practical purposes ΔH^\ddagger can be taken equal to ΔE^\ddagger (Refs. 1-4).

Equation (1) has the advantage that the effects of solvent on the reaction potential surface can be incorporated, at least in principle, through ΔS^\ddagger and ΔH^\ddagger . However, one must then make the additional assumption that the solvent molecules are in equilibrium with the reacting system at all times during the reaction. For a fast reaction involving movement of polar or ionic groups in a polar solvent, the above assumption of complete equilibrium at all stages of the reaction may breakdown. This is because for a fast reaction, the solvent molecules will not be able to rearrange sufficiently rapidly to follow its equilibrium path. There will be some degree of non-equilibrium solvation in the transition state or its neighbourhood.

We can make the above discussion more quantitative by defining (somewhat arbitrarily) an average life-time τ^\ddagger of the transition state. In a one dimensional model, τ^\ddagger can be defined by the following relation¹,

$$\tau^\ddagger = \frac{\Delta l}{v} \quad (2)$$

where, Δl is the length of a segment of reaction coordinate in the neighbourhood of the transition state—this length defines a 'transition state like' complex (Fig. 1), and v is the velocity of the reacting

Fig. 1. Curve of a one-dimensional potential energy surface plotted against the reaction coordinate (Q). The length Δl denotes a neighbourhood of the transition state.

system across the barrier. We want to compare τ^\ddagger with the solvent relaxation time τ defined through

$$\tau = \mu_{solv} / \zeta \quad (3)$$

where, μ_{solv} is the effective mass of the solvent relaxation and ζ is the relevant friction parameter. An estimate of v can be obtained from kinetic theory,

$$v = (2k_B T / \mu)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where, μ is the effective mass of the reaction. For an isomerisation reaction $\mu \approx 100$ amu, so $v \approx 2 \times 10^4$ cm s⁻¹ at 300 K. Estimation of Δl is tricky. Approximately this can be set equal to the interval between the points where the barrier height is half of its maximum. Assuming that the barrier is an inverted parabola with barrier frequency 10^{13} s⁻¹ and barrier height 5 kcal mol⁻¹, we obtain $\Delta l \approx 10^{-8}$ cm. This gives $\tau^\ddagger \approx 5 \times 10^{-13}$ s. This value of τ^\ddagger is comparable to the value of τ for many liquids. This implies that a clear separation of time scales may not exist between τ^\ddagger and τ and as a result, the assumption of complete solvation at every stage of the reaction may breakdown making the TST expression for the rate constant (equation (1)) unreliable.

In the *Non-equilibrium solvation dynamics* section we shall consider the effects of non-equilibrium solvation on photochemical reactions in more detail.

Kramers' theory: It is known that rates of many chemical reactions depend strongly on viscosity of the solvent. This is especially true for those reactions which involve a spatial rearrangement of molecular groups as the rate determining step of the reaction. The transition state theory, however, totally ignores this dynamical aspect of solvent forces. In solution phase reactions the main assumption of TST, that no trajectory crosses the dividing surface more than once, breaks down. The frictional forces exerted by the solvent induce recrossings of the trajectories and reduce the rate below the TST value. The most well known theory of viscosity dependence of rate is due to Kramers¹⁶. In the following we briefly review Kramers' theory.

In order to study the effects of solvent frictional forces on the rate of a chemical reaction in solution,

Kramers' modelled the reactive motion as the passage of a Brownian particle over a one-dimensional potential barrier. Kramers' assumed that the motion along the reaction coordinate is given by the following ordinary Langevin equation^{8,17},

$$\mu \frac{dv}{dt} = F(x) - \zeta v(t) + f(t) \quad (5)$$

where, μ and v are respectively the effective mass and the velocity along the reaction coordinate, $F(x)$ is the force arising from the potential in the barrier region, ζ is the zero-frequency friction parameter and $f(t)$ is the delta-correlated white noise. ζ and $f(t)$ are related by the fluctuation-dissipation theorem^{8,17},

$$\langle f(0)f(t) \rangle = k_B T \delta(t) \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) is known as the white-noise approximation for the random force. $F(x)$ is assumed to arise from a static potential which is an inverted parabola

$$F = \mu \omega_b^2 x \quad (7)$$

The details of Kramers' analysis is easily available ; here, we quote the final expression for the rate constant given by

$$k = \frac{\omega_R}{2\pi\omega_b} \left[\left(\frac{\zeta^2}{4} + \omega_b^2 \right)^{1/2} - \frac{\zeta}{2} \right] e^{-E_0/k_B T} \quad (8)$$

where, ω_R is the frequency of the (assumed harmonic) reactant well and E_0 is the molecular activation energy of the one dimensional potential surface. Equation (8) has two important limiting properties. If $2\omega_b \gg \zeta$, then one obtains the TST result of this model with a rate constant independent of the friction parameter ζ . In the opposite limit, when $2\omega_b \ll \zeta$, then equation (8) predicts a rate constant inversely proportional to the friction,

$$k = k^{SL} = \frac{\omega_R \omega_b}{2\pi \zeta} e^{-E_0/k_B T} \quad (9)$$

This limit is known as the Smoluchowski limit. In the next section we shall examine the validity of this limit.

Kramers' theory provides us with a simple and elegant expression for the frictional dependence of the rate. Unfortunately, this theory has some drawbacks which limit its applicability. In the following we briefly mention the two most important limitations of the Kramers' theory.

(i) Kramers' treatment is one-dimensional. For reactions in large molecules, there may be several non-reactive modes that interact strongly with the reactive mode.

(ii) The assumption that the solvent forces on the reactive motion are delta-correlated (equation (6)) in time is subject to suspect for sharp barriers for which ω_b^{-1} is smaller than the bath correlation time at high viscosities. In this limit, the reactant may not stay long enough at the barrier top to probe all the solvent motions. The zero-frequency friction then *overestimates* the solvent drag on the reactive

motion and one must take into account the frequency dependence of the friction. That is, equation (6) is to be discarded and retention of the 'memory' of solvent forces is necessary to obtain a consistent description.

In the next section we consider the effects of the frequency dependence of friction on the reaction rate. We shall see that the memory- or the non-Markovian effects can alter the viscosity dependence of the rate constant qualitatively.

Non-Markovian effects :

Recent experimental studies⁸⁻¹¹ on photochemical isomerisation of several large organic molecules in solution, have indicated an apparent breakdown of the well known Kramers' theory¹⁰. The most important result of these investigations is that Kramers' theory does not have the correct *curvature* to describe the viscosity dependence of the rate at both high and low viscosities. Velsko *et al.*¹⁰ found that their results could be fitted very well to a viscosity dependence of the following form,

$$k = A_0 \eta^{-\alpha} \exp(-E_0/k_B T) \quad (10)$$

where, A_0 is a viscosity independent constant, E_0 is the *isoviscous* activation energy and η is the zero-frequency shear viscosity. The value of the exponent α lies in the range $1 \gg \alpha \gg 0.1$ with $\alpha = 0.26$ for the ground state DODCI and $\alpha = 0.43$ for the excited state DODCI¹⁰. For the excited state diphenyl butadiene (DPB), $\alpha = 0.59$ fits the experimental data well⁹. At the viscosities studied in the above experiments, Kramers' theory predicts $\alpha = 1$, i.e. the attainment of the Smoluchowski limit¹⁷. This non-attainment of the Smoluchowski limit is remarkable and is the subject of the present discussion.

The precise reason for the breakdown of Kramers' theory at high viscosities is still far from understood. There are two different explanations that have been put forward. The first explanation is based on the experimental fact, that the magnitude of the exponent α correlates well with the frequency ω_b of the potential barrier. If ω_b is small, then $\alpha = 1$, but if ω_b is large (which implies a sharp barrier), then α is much less than unity. Since ω_b^{-1} is a measure of the 'residence time' τ^* , near the barrier top, it appears that the frequency dependence of solvent friction may play an important role in the breakdown of Kramers' theory^{9,10}. A different explanation that has been advocated⁹ for the breakdown of Kramers' theory is based on multidimensional nature of the potential surface. In a large molecule, there are many degrees of freedom that can be coupled with the reactive degree of motion. Since Kramers' theory is a one-dimensional theory, this multidimensionality of the potential surface can significantly modify the predictions of Kramers' theory. In fact, it can be shown that an adiabatic coupling between the reactive mode and other non-reactive modes of the reacting molecule is essentially equivalent to a frequency dependent friction in a one-dimensional picture. The form of the frequency dependent friction is, however, different in this case^{8,9,10}

The effects of the frequency dependence of friction on the rates of chemical reactions in solution have been investigated by various authors in recent years²¹⁻²⁶. We mention the work of Bagchi and Oxtoby²⁴ who showed, by using the hydrodynamic expression of Zwanzig and Bixon²³, that the non-Markovian theory of Grote and Hynes²¹ can qualitatively explain the experimental results of Velsko *et al.*^{9,10}. Bagchi and Oxtoby²⁴ observed that the breakdown of Kramers' theory occurs because the *effective* friction in the barrier region is much smaller than its zero-frequency value at high viscosities for sharp barriers. These authors argued that if the barrier is too high and sharp, frequency dependence of friction will play an important role and the Smoluchowski limit may never be realised, in total breakdown of Kramers' theory. However, this conclusion of Bagchi and Oxtoby²⁴ is perplexing and contradicts the traditional belief. One serious limitation of the argument of these authors is that it depends heavily on the Maxwell forms for the frequency dependence of viscosity assumed in their work. Another problem is that the conclusion is based on numerical solution of Grote-Hynes theory. In this section we shall reexamine this problem by using a different approach.

We start with the following expression for the rate constant, k , for a one-dimensional reaction²¹,

$$k = k^{TS}(\lambda_r/\omega_b) \quad (11)$$

where, k^{TS} is the transition state rate constant given by

$$k^{TS} = \frac{\omega_b}{2\pi} \exp(-E_0/k_B T) \quad (12)$$

where, ω_b is frequency of motion in the reactant well and ω_b is the barrier frequency. λ_r is given by the following self-consistent relation²¹,

$$\lambda_r = \frac{\omega_b^2}{\lambda_r + \zeta(\lambda_r)/\mu} \quad (13)$$

where, μ is the effective mass of reactive motion. $\zeta(\lambda_r)$ is the Laplace transform of the time dependent friction $\zeta(t)$.

$$\hat{\zeta}(\lambda_r) = \int_0^\infty dt e^{-\lambda_r t} \zeta(t) \quad (14)$$

Equation (13) predicts the transition state result for very weak friction ($\lambda_r \sim \omega_b$) and the Kramers' result for low barrier frequency, *i.e.*, $\omega_b \rightarrow 0$, so that $\hat{\zeta}(\lambda_r)$ may be replaced by $\hat{\zeta}(0)$. If the barrier frequency is large ($\omega_b \geq 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$) then the situation is not so straightforward and one must solve equation (13) to obtain λ_r . Bagchi and Oxtoby²⁴ used the Zwanzig-Bixon expression²³ for $\hat{\zeta}(\lambda_r)$. The expression is rather cumbersome, so we write it symbolically as

$$\hat{\zeta}(p) = F(p, \eta_s(p), \eta_v(p), c, \rho_0, R, \beta) \quad (15)$$

The functional form of F (in Laplace plane) is given elsewhere²⁴. In equation (15), $\eta_s(p)$ and $\eta_v(p)$

are the frequency dependent shear and bulk viscosities, respectively, ρ_0 is the solvent density, c is the velocity of sound, β is the slip parameter, zero for pure slip and infinity for stick boundary conditions, and R is the hydrodynamic radius of the reactive moiety. For isomerisation reactions, the reactive motion is a twisting motion of a part of the organic molecule around a molecule-fixed axis.

Bagchi and Oxtoby²⁴ assumed simple Maxwell forms for $\eta_s(p)$ and $\eta_v(p)$

$$\eta_s(p) = \frac{\eta_s^0}{1 + p \tau_s} \quad (16a)$$

$$\eta_v(p) = \frac{\eta_v^0}{1 + p \tau_v} \quad (16b)$$

where, η_s^0 and η_v^0 are respectively the zero frequency shear and bulk viscosities. The viscoelastic relaxation constants τ_s and τ_v are given by⁴⁰

$$\tau_s = \frac{\eta_s^0}{G_\infty}; \quad \tau_v = \frac{\eta_v^0}{K_r} \quad (17)$$

where, G_∞ is the infinite frequency shear viscosity and K_r is the relaxation part of the bulk modulus⁴⁰. Subsequent analysis of the viscosity dependence of the rate constant, especially of the non-attainment of the Smoluchowski limit at high viscosity for sharp potential barriers, depend crucially on the functional relations between $\eta_s(p)$, η_v^0 and τ_s (for details, Ref. 24). Therefore, the conclusions derived are also valid only to the extent these relations are reliable.

In this section we present an alternative analysis based on an asymptotic form of $\hat{\zeta}(p)$. Here, it is possible to obtain an analytic expression for k without using the Maxwell forms and the relations (17).

For simplicity we assume that the reactive motion is translation of a sphere of radius R and mass m in a liquid of density ρ_0 . We consider the fluid to be incompressible, *i.e.* the sound velocity c . In this limit the expression for $\hat{\zeta}(p)$ simplifies and is given by⁴¹

$$\hat{\zeta}(p) = \frac{9M\nu}{2R^2} \left[1 + R \left(\frac{p}{\nu} \right)^{1/2} + \frac{pR^2}{9\nu} \right] \quad (18)$$

where, ν is the kinetic viscosity and M is the mass of the displaced fluid. ν and M are given by

$$\nu = \frac{\eta}{\rho_0}; \quad M = \frac{4\pi}{3} R^3 \rho_0 \quad (19)$$

Next, we substitute equation (18) into the self-consistent condition (equation (13)) to obtain the following equation,

$$A\lambda_r^2 + B\nu^{1/2} \lambda_r^{3/2} + C\nu\lambda_r = \omega_b^2 \quad (20)$$

where,

$$A = 1 + M/2\mu \quad (21a)$$

$$B = \frac{9M}{2\mu R} \quad (21b)$$

$$C = \frac{9M}{2\mu R^2} \quad (21c)$$

Equation (20) has several interesting features. Firstly, in the limit $\nu \rightarrow 0$, we find $\lambda_r = \frac{1}{\sqrt{A}} \omega_b$, i.e.

a 'transition state type' result (for k is equal to k^{TST} only when $\lambda_r = \omega_b$). A is of the order of unity, so the difference is small. The reason for the non-attainment of the TST result is that for incompressible fluid, the initial condition for the velocity correlation function exhibits a lack of continuity. The discrepancy is eliminated if compressibility is taken into account. This discrepancy definitely affects quantitative result but has no influence on the qualitative conclusions of this section.

In the limit of large viscosity (i.e. $\nu \rightarrow \infty$), we recover the Smoluchowski limit

$$k \rightarrow \frac{\omega_b}{C\nu} k^{TST}, \quad (22)$$

i.e. rate is inversely proportional to the macroscopic viscosity. This result seems to indicate that the earlier conclusion of Bagchi and Oxtoby²⁴ on the non-attainment of the Smoluchowski limit for sharp barriers is limited to liquids obeying Maxwell forms for viscoelastic relaxations.

The most interesting feature of equation (20) is, however, manifested in the intermediate regime of viscosity. In this regime, equation (20) exhibits a non-analytic dependence of the rate on the viscosity parameter ν . What is more important is the range over which the non-analytic dependence holds. In order to study this aspect, we use the following estimates, which are taken to mimic isomerisation of DPB, $\rho_0 = 1 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $R = 3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}$, $M = 3.4 \times 10^{-23} \text{ g}$ and $\mu = 1.6 \times 10^{-22} \text{ g}$, to obtain the following equation,

$$2.05 x^2 + (\nu')^{1/2} x^{3/2} + 0.1 \nu' x = 1 \quad (23)$$

where,

$$x = \lambda_r / \omega_b \quad (24a)$$

$$\nu' = B^2 \nu / \omega_b \quad (24b)$$

There is a slight approximation involved in using equation (23) to study the effects of viscosity because we have fixed the solvent density yet varying the viscosity. If viscosity is changed by varying temperature then the solvent density will not be much affected whereas viscosity is a strong function of temperature. This justifies the use of equation (23). It may be noted that the prefactor of the term linear in ν' in equation (23) is small. Therefore, one may have to reach a very large value of ν' before the Smoluchowski behaviour is obtained.

We have plotted the solution of equation (23) in Fig. 2. The dependence of the rate parameter x on viscosity parameter ν' is surprisingly similar to the results obtained earlier²⁴. The graph has a viscosity dependence which is qualitatively similar to the experimental results of Velsko *et al.*^{9,10}. However, a quantitative comparison between theory and experiment is meaningless at this stage because of the approximations that are involved in deriving

equation (20) and the uncertainty in the values of the potential parameters.

Fig. 2. The rate parameter $x(=\lambda_r/\omega_b)$ is plotted against the reduced viscosity parameter ν' , as obtained by solving equation (23) of the text.

As mentioned earlier, equation (20) predicts Smoluchowski behaviour for large values of ν . For the values of parameters chosen in obtaining equation (23), it is possible to obtain a rough estimate of the value of ν required to produce Smoluchowski limit. From equation (23), SL is obtained around $\nu' \approx 100$. For $\omega_b = 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$, we get $\eta \approx 1 \text{ cp}$ which is too small a value to obtain SL. Clearly equation (23) is not reliable for quantitative purposes. This point deserves further study. It is surprising that compressibility (or acoustic dissipation) would play such an important role.

Non-equilibrium solvation dynamics :

The non-Markovian effect discussed in the last section focuses on the failure of the solvent motions to 'track' the fast reactive motion at the barrier. This effect can be termed 'dynamical non-equilibrium' effect. The assumption made is that the barrier height and the barrier shape remain unchanged within a homologous series of solvents. Another related assumption is that the reacting molecule is fully solvated at each point along the reaction coordinate so that the potential surface is time independent. In the following we briefly discuss the range of validity of the last assumption.

If the solute-solvent interactions are dominated by short-range forces, then the equilibrium solvation hypothesis may be reliable. The situation changes drastically if the solute molecule possesses a large dipole moment and the solvent is highly polar. In many experimentally studied cases, the dipole moment of the solute molecule is different in the excited state from its value in the ground state^{4,9}. Therefore, a solvent reorganisation follows the excitation. Since the polar interactions are long ranged, the time of solvent reorganisation towards the new equilibrium may be comparable to the time scale of the reacting event. In such a situation,

which is quite common in experiments, the equilibrium solvation hypothesis will break down.

In order to understand the non-equilibrium solvation effects on photochemical reactions, we shall consider the following two situations. (A) The reacting event is a radiationless 'jump' from a minimum in the excited state surface to a maximum on the ground state surface (Fig. 3). In the terminology of photochemistry, this is a 'diabatic' photoreaction^{43,44}. The reactive motion is the motion on the excited potential surface from the initial position to the reactive region. The reactive motion is controlled by the potential surface and the solvent viscous forces. We consider the case where the permanent dipole moment of the molecule changes significantly on excitation. (B) The reactive motion involves a thermally assisted crossing of an activation barrier on the excited state potential surface (Fig. 4). The activation barrier height E_0 is such that $E_0/k_B T \geq 5$.

Fig. 3. A typical potential energy diagram for a photochemical reaction which occurs without the intervention of an activation barrier. The solid arrows indicate the positions of the excitation and the 'jump'. The dashed line denotes the reactive motion on the excited surface.

Fig. 4. A typical potential energy diagram for an 'adiabatic' photoreaction where the rate limiting step is a thermally assisted crossing of an activation barrier.

Recent experiments on triphenylmethane (TPM) molecules^{14,15} and on dimethylaminogenzonitrile (DMABN)⁶ have revealed the effects of solvent polarity on photochemical reactions in solution. These experiments showed that the solvent polarity can modify the reaction potential surface to the extent that a crossover from the zero barrier (case (i)) to a finite activation barrier (case (ii)) can take

place. We shall discuss the mechanism of such a crossover after our discussion of the two cases.

Case (A) : Reaction in the absence of a barrier : On excitation to higher electronic states, both the magnitude and the direction of the permanent dipole moment can undergo significant changes. Since the process of optical excitation and emission are much faster than any relaxation processes involved, we model the change in dipole moment on excitation and fluorescence by Heaviside functions

$$\underline{\mu}^{(b)}(t) = \underline{\mu}_g^{(b)} + H(t=0)[\underline{\mu}_e^{(b)} - \underline{\mu}_g^{(b)}] + H(t=t_1)[\underline{\mu}_g^{(b)} - \underline{\mu}_e^{(b)}] \quad (25)$$

where, $\underline{\mu}_g^{(b)}$ and $\underline{\mu}_e^{(b)}$ are the dipole moments in the body-fixed frame to the solute molecule in the ground and excited states, respectively. $H(t)$ is a Heaviside function. Equation (25) is simply a statement of the fact that the molecule is excited from its ground electronic state at time $t=0$ and it fluoresces back at time $t=t_1$. The time t_1 will, however, be determined by the interaction within the system (solute+solvent). The average of t_1 is essentially the time-constant which we want to calculate.

It may be noted that the dipole moments $\underline{\mu}_g^{(b)}$ and $\underline{\mu}_e^{(b)}$ are given in the body-fixed frame. In a photochemical reaction, the reactive motion may involve a rotational or torsional motion of a part of the reacting molecule with respect to the rest. In such a situation the reactive motion may be coupled to the rotational motion of the dipole moment in the space-fixed frame. Let us briefly consider this point. The origin of rotational motion is random collisions with other solvent molecules. In the liquid phase, the rotational motion will hardly experience any systematic potential, except the reaction-field of the dipole moment itself in polar liquids. However, the effect of this reaction-field does not qualitatively change the nature of the diffusion process. The reactive motion, on the other hand, may involve some particular rearrangements of molecular groups and will usually experience a restoring force. The reactive motion will also experience random collisions with the solvent molecules so the reactive motion is sort of a diffusion in a force-field. Let us consider a specific example, *p*-dimethylaminonitrile. In the excited state this molecule develops a charge separation between the phenyl and the amino group, thereby generating a large change in dipole moment⁶. The reactive motion (shown by an arrow in Fig. 5) hardly changes the direction of the dipole moment, although the magnitude of the excited state dipole moment may change significantly. In this case, the dipolar motion is not *explicitly* coupled to the reactive motion, although the potential surface for reactive motion may depend on dipolar motion. First, we consider the effect of dipolar motion on the photochemical reaction by neglecting the direct coupling between the rotational motion of the dipole and the reactive motion. Because of this approximation, the effects of

dipolar interactions enter only in the average, time dependent, stabilisation energy of the excited state potential surface.

Fig. 5. The reactive motion in the excited *p*-dimethylamino-nitrile is shown by an arrow. The motion leads to a significant separation of charge density as indicated in the figure.

Let $\langle E_s \rangle_{g,a}^0$ and $\langle E_s \rangle_{e,a}^0$ denote the average stabilisation energies due to dipolar interactions in the ground and excited states of the solute molecule in equilibrium with the polar solvent. $\langle E_f \rangle_g^0$ is the interaction energy when the excited molecule is in the Franck-Condon state of the ground-state solvent configuration and $\langle E_f \rangle_e^0$ denotes the reverse situation. Let $\langle E_s(t) \rangle^e$ denote the time-dependent stabilisation energy when the molecule is in the excited state at a time t after the optical excitation. Obviously $\langle E_s(t \rightarrow \infty) \rangle^e = \langle E_s \rangle_{e,a}^0$. If Q denotes the reaction coordinate, then the energy difference between the excited and the ground surface is given by

$$\Delta E_{eg}(t, Q) = \langle E_s(t, Q) \rangle^e - \langle E_f(t, Q) \rangle_g^0 \quad (26)$$

Later in this section we shall give an explicit expression for $\Delta E_{eg}(t, Q)$ from dielectric continuum theory. Let us now study the limiting properties of equation (26). In the limit $t \rightarrow \infty$, we have the equilibrium solvation of the excited state and $\langle E_f(t, Q) \rangle_g^0$ becomes equal to $\langle E_f \rangle_g^0$ so that equation (26) becomes

$$\Delta E_{eg}(\infty) = \langle E_s \rangle_{e,a}^0 - \langle E_f \rangle_g^0 \quad (27)$$

In equation (27) and hereafter we have dropped Q for convenience. In the limit $t \rightarrow 0$, equation (26) reduces to

$$\Delta E_{eg}(0) = \langle E_f \rangle_e^0 - \langle E_s \rangle_{g,a}^0 \quad (28)$$

If the reaction is slow or the solvent relaxation is fast, then the reaction probes only the contribution $\Delta E_{eg}(\infty)$, and this effect is well-studied. However, interesting things may happen when the reaction competes with $\Delta E_{eg}(t)$. This is the regime what we call non-equilibrium solvation regime. Before we develop a mathematical formulation of this problem, let us consider the following three regimes.

- (i) Solvent is frozen. Then relaxation occurs from the same environment to which it is initially excited.
- (ii) Solvent relaxation is much faster than the reaction. In this case equilibrium solvation is an adequate representation.
- (iii) Solvent relaxation and reaction rate are comparable to each other. This is the non-equilibrium solvation regime.

A clear evidence of the existence of non-equilibrium solvation dynamics comes from the experimentally observed time evolution of fluorescence Stokes shift of polar molecules in polar solvents^{45,46}.

In many cases, the maximum of the fluorescence spectra changes from a significant blue shift at short times to a red shift at longer times where the shifts are measured with respect to the fluorescence in non-polar solvents. The time evolution of these shifts can be explained in terms of the stabilisation energies of the ground and the excited states⁴⁷. We shall show below that these same stabilisation energies play a crucial role in determining the rate of a photochemical reaction, and in some cases, may even alter the course of the reaction.

Let us briefly discuss the essence of the solvent effects. Let the dipole moment of the excited state has a large magnitude but retains the same direction (i.e. $|\mu_e| > |\mu_g|$ and $\underline{\mu}_e \parallel \underline{\mu}_g$). Then the following relations hold,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{eg}(0) &< 0 \\ \Delta E_{eg}(\infty) &< 0 \\ \text{and } \Delta E_{eg}(\infty) &< \Delta E_{eg}(0) \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

i.e. the long time energy difference between the two states is less than the initial difference. The situation is illustrated pictorially in Fig. 6. Now the time evolution of $\Delta E_{eg}(t)$ enters into the dynamics of the photochemical reaction in the following

Fig. 6 The variation of the reaction potential energy surface as a result of solvation of a dipolar molecule in a polar solvent. The legends 'i' and 'f' denote the initial and final states, respectively.

manner. The rate of 'jump' or internal conversion from the excited surface to the ground surface is an exponential function of the energy gap⁴⁸. We write this dependence in the following form,

$$k_{nr}(x, t) = k_0 S(x) \exp[-\alpha \Delta E_{eg}(t)] \quad (30)$$

where, k_0 is the rate of radiation-less transition from the minimum of the excited state potential surface (where the rate is maximum) in non-polar solvents, $S(x)$ is the sink function which gives the position dependence of the decay (Ref. 31 may be seen for a discussion on the sink function $S(x)$) and α is a constant which, like k_0 , is a molecular property. The important thing to note is the exponential dependence of the rate on $\Delta E_{eg}(t)$. If the dipole moment of the excited surface changes by a significant amount or undergoes a significant rotation, then k_{nr} may change sufficiently rapidly with time to compete with the overall decay rate

of the excited state population. Next we proceed to calculate this population decay rate.

In the present case, there is no high barrier for the reactive motion so one must solve for the time dependent probability of the system remaining on the excited state surface. In our model, the radiationless relaxation is represented by a position dependent sink. The motion along the potential surface is governed by the force from the potential (approximated as harmonic) and the viscous drag of the solvent. We model all these competing factors by a modified Smoluchowski equation of the following form³¹,

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t}(x, t) = A \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2}(x, t) + B \frac{\partial}{\partial x} xP(x, t) - k_{nr}(x, t) P(x, t) \quad (31)$$

where, $A = k_B T / \zeta$ and $B = \omega^2 \mu / \zeta$, ω being the frequency of motion on the excited surface, ζ the relevant friction coefficient, μ the reduced mass of the reactive motion. $k_{nr}(x, t)$ is given by equation (30).

Several choices of the sink function were considered in Ref. 31. Here, we assume a Gaussian form centred at the minimum of the excited state potential surface

$$S(x) = e^{-x^2/a^2} \quad (32)$$

where, a is related to the width of the sink. The Gaussian sink is quite realistic because the energy difference between two harmonic surfaces is a quadratic function of x , and so the exponential energy gap law predicts a shifted Gaussian probability distribution for the transition probability between two surfaces.

With the choice of sink function (equation 32), it has not been possible to solve equation (31) analytically. Instead, it may be solved by a series expansion. We define an operator \mathcal{L} by

$$\mathcal{L} = B \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{A}{B} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + x \right) \quad (33)$$

We expand $P(x, t)$ in the eigenfunctions of the Fokker-Planck operator \mathcal{L}

$$P(x, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sigma_n(t) b_n(x) \quad (34)$$

where $b_n(x)$ is the n -th eigenfunction of \mathcal{L} (Ref. 31),

$$\mathcal{L} b_n = -n B b_n \quad (35)$$

$$b_n(x) = A_n^{1/2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2V^2}\right) H_n\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2V}}\right) \quad (36)$$

where, H_n is the Hermite polynomial of order n , $V = (A/B)^{1/2}$ and the normalisation constant A_n is given by

$$A_n = (V n! 2^n \sqrt{2\pi})^{-1} \quad (37)$$

The conjugate eigenfunction b_n^+ is defined through³¹,

$$b_n^+ \mathcal{L} = -n B b_n^+ \quad (38a)$$

$$b_n^+ = A_n^{1/2} H_n\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{2V}}\right) \quad (38b)$$

b_n and b_n^+ are orthonormal. Following the usual procedure, we obtain the following system of equations for $\sigma_m(t)$,

$$\sigma_m(t) = -m B \sigma_m(t) - k_0 \exp[-\alpha \Delta E_{eg}(t)] \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (A_n A_m)^{1/2} I_{m,n} \sigma_n(t) \quad (39)$$

where,

$$I_{m,n} = (-1)^{\frac{m+n}{2}} 2^{m+n+\frac{1}{2}} V \left(1 + \frac{a^2}{2V^2}\right)^{-\frac{m+n}{2}} \otimes \left(\frac{a^2}{a^2 + 2V^2}\right)^{1/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{m+n+1}{2}\right) {}_2F_1\left(-m, -n; \frac{1-m-n}{2}; \frac{a^2 + 2V^2}{4V^2}\right), \quad (m+n) \text{ even} \quad (40)$$

where, ${}_2F_1$ is an ordinary hypergeometric function⁴⁸ defined as

$${}_2F_1(a, b, c; Z) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_i (b)_i}{(c)_i} \frac{Z^i}{i!} \quad (41)$$

$(Y)_i$ is Pochhammer's symbol⁴⁸. In the present case, both a and b are either negative integers or zero, so ${}_2F_1$ is a polynomial with the upper limit of the sum (equation (41)) at $\min(m, n)$.

Equation (39) can be solved numerically to obtain the time dependent probability distribution $P(t)$. However, we need an expression for $\Delta E_{eg}(t)$ for such a calculation. Next, we present an expression for $\Delta E_{eg}(t)$.

Expression for $\Delta E_{eg}(t)$: We assume that the dominant contribution to $E_{eg}(t)$ comes from dipolar interaction energy which we write in the following form⁴⁷,

$$\Delta E(t) = -\frac{1}{2}(\epsilon_0 + 2) \underline{\mu}(t) \cdot \int_{-\infty}^t dt' r(t-t') \underline{\mu}(t') \quad (42)$$

where, $r(t)$ is given, in the Debye approximation, by the following expression,

$$r(t) = \frac{2}{3R^3 \epsilon_0 \tau_D} \left[(\epsilon_0 + 2) / (2\epsilon_\infty + \epsilon_0) \right] \times \left[\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty + \frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)(\epsilon_0 + 2\epsilon_0)}{\epsilon_0 + 2\epsilon_\infty} \right] e^{-t/\tau_L} = \frac{3}{\epsilon_0 + 2} F e^{-t/\tau_L} \quad (43)$$

where,

$$\tau_L = \frac{\epsilon_0 + 2\epsilon_\infty}{\epsilon_0 + 2\epsilon_0} \tau_D \quad (44)$$

where, F is defined by equation (43), ϵ_0 and ϵ_∞ are respectively the zero frequency and infinite frequency dielectric constants of the polar solvent, τ_D is the Debye relaxation time constant of the medium, ϵ_0 and R are the infinite frequency dielectric constant and the radius of the solute particle (approximated by a sphere), respectively.

Two comments on equations (42-44) are in order. Firstly, these expressions are derived with the assumption that the solvent is a dielectric continuum and that the response function of the solvent is given adequately by a frequency dependent dielectric constant. Secondly, a simple Debye relaxation form⁴⁰,

$$\epsilon(\omega) = \epsilon_{\infty} + \frac{\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_{\infty}}{1 - i\omega\tau_D} \quad (45)$$

is assumed for $\epsilon(\omega)$. This is obviously a simplifying approximation and can be easily improved⁴⁰ by using a more realistic form for $\epsilon(\omega)$. The spherical shape assumption for the solute particle is also not realistic, but this assumption is not expected to affect the qualitative or semi-quantitative conclusions of this work.

Using the above expressions, some straightforward manipulations lead to the following expression for $\Delta E_{eg}(t)$ ⁴⁷,

$$\Delta E_{eg}(t) = F\tau_r(\mu_0\mu_g \cos\psi - \mu_0^2)(1 - e^{-t/\tau_r}) + F\tau_r(\mu_0^2 - \mu_0\mu_g \cos\psi)e^{-t/\tau_r} \quad (45)$$

where, $\tau_r^{-1} = \tau_r^{-1} + 2D$, and ψ is the angle of rotation of the dipole upon excitation, measured in the body-fixed frame, and D is the rotational diffusion coefficient of the solute molecule.

Equation (39) can now be solved numerically to obtain $P(t)$. A similar calculation was carried out elsewhere³¹. Equation (39) is a straightforward generalisation of the above mentioned work to consider non-equilibrium solvation dynamics.

A detailed numerical solution of equation (39), with $\Delta E_{eg}(t)$ given by equation (46), will be presented elsewhere. However, several interesting qualitative features of the solvent effect on the reaction rate can be drawn from the analytic structure of the above equations and are given below.

(i) If the reaction rate is much faster than the solvent relaxation rate (both k_0 and ω are large so that rate of decay is larger than solvent relaxation rate), then the electronic relaxation occurs from the excited state which is Franck-Condon state of the ground state. If the dipole moment (in the body-fixed frame) rotates by more than $\pi/2$ but less than $3\pi/2$ on excitation, then the excited Franck-Condon state can have significantly larger separation from the ground state than what would be present when both the states are in equilibrium with the surrounding solvent. This effect would tend to reduce the rate of reaction. On the other hand, if the rotation of the dipole moment is such that $\pi/2 \geq \psi \geq -\pi/2$ then the reaction rate can increase because of this non-equilibrium effect.

(ii) If the reaction rate is much slower than the solvent relaxation then the reaction would occur from the excited state in equilibrium with the surrounding solvent. In this case the theory of equilibrium solvation is applicable.

(iii) In the general case where no such separation of time scales exists, we expect the non-equilibrium solvation dynamics to influence the rate of the reaction significantly. In this case the decay function $P(t)$ will show departure from the decay function evaluated at solvent equilibrium at the initial and the intermediate times. There are several scenarios that are possible. If the excited molecule finds the initial environment unfavourable, then the initial decay would be slower than the equilibrium decay. A schematic representation of the decay behaviour is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. The time evolution of the excited state population $P(t)$. The dashed line is result from Ref. 31. The solid line includes the effect of non-equilibrium solvation.

There may be an interesting side-effect of this slow initial decay of the excited state from an unfavourable solvent environment. It may lead to an adiabatic reaction with a finite non-zero activation barrier. A crossover behaviour of this type has been observed recently by Sundstron and Gillbro¹⁶ in their experiments on solvent dependence of electronic relaxation of TPM dyes.

Case (B) : Reaction in the presence of a barrier : In this case the non-equilibrium solvation dynamics can affect the rate and even the course of the reaction if the reaction coordinate is coupled to solvent relaxation. One simple way in which this coupling can occur is the following. It may be considered that the reactive motion is a twist of one part of the solute molecule around the other. Such a twisting motion can lead to a change in the magnitude and in the direction of the dipole moment. Depending on the state of solvent polarisation around the solute molecule, the activated complex may be stabilised or destabilised. In the former case, the activation barrier that would be probed by the reactive motion would be less than that in a

non-polar solvent, and the reverse is true if the activated complex is destabilised.

One recently studied example is the isomerisation of dimethylaminobenzonitrile (DMABN) in polar media⁹. In the excited state, this molecule undergoes a rotation of the dimethylamino group about the amino-phenyl bond. The motion results in a charge separation and the twisted form develops a large dipole moment. The reaction is shown in Fig. 5, where the reactive motion is shown by an arrow. In this case, experiments seem to indicate that the dipole moment changes by a rapid jump near the product well followed by solvent stabilisation. Obviously, several other scenerios are also possible. In the case of DMABN, the potential parameters of the reaction change with the polarity of the solvent. If the reaction is faster than solvent relaxation (which may be true in an associated liquid) then the effect of non-equilibrium solvation dynamics may become important.

At present, there is no reliable theoretical calculation for these non-equilibrium effects. van der Zwan and Hynes^{29,30} have carried out some model calculations to show the importance of these non-equilibrium effects, but their model is not very realistic. Further work on this field would certainly be worthwhile.

Discussion

It is evident from the preceding analysis that non-equilibrium solvation dynamics can profoundly affect the kinetics of a chemical reaction in solution. In order to enable experimental study of the novel effects discussed in this paper, the reacting system (reactant(s)+solvent) must satisfy the following conditions. (i) The rate of the chemical reaction must be comparable to the relevant solvent relaxation rate. (ii) The reactive event must involve a change in a molecular property which can alter the reaction potential energy surface *via* coupling of this property to the surrounding solvent. Obviously dipole moment is such a molecular property whose change in a polar solvent can have a significant effect on the potential energy surface.

It is obvious that photochemical isomerisation reactions in polar solvents are good candidates for the study of the non-equilibrium solvation effects. These effects are likely to be important in picosecond or in subpicosecond regime. Further theoretical and experimental studies to understand the role of non-equilibrium solvation processes in chemical reactions in solution will certainly be worthwhile.

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